

Summary of Code Patterns for Each Risk

Mstore Misoptimization.

- (1) Legacy Code Generation Pipeline: The legacy pipeline runs the Yul optimizer on inline assembly blocks individually, leading to incorrect memory optimizations.
- (2) Inline Assembly Blocks: The inline assembly blocks do not refer to any variables defined in the surrounding Solidity code; Memory writes within such assembly blocks are removed if the memory is not read within the same block.
- (3) Subsequent Access to Written Memory: Memory written in one assembly block is accessed in a subsequent assembly block, leading to potential errors due to removed writes.
- (4) Fixed Memory Offsets: Use of fixed memory offsets for intermediate values between assembly blocks, which can cause unexpected overwrites if the writes are removed.
- (5) Static Memory Reservation: Attempts to reserve static memory by modifying the free memory pointer, which can be incorrectly optimized out, leading to incorrect memory states.

Storage Excessive Deletion.

- (1) Use of Optimized Code Generation: The vulnerability is more likely to occur with optimized via-IR code generation, but it can also theoretically happen in optimized legacy code generation.
- (2) Inline Assembly with return(...) or stop(): The vulnerability requires the use of inline assembly blocks that contain the return(...) or stop() instructions.
- (3) Storage Write Before Conditional Termination: A storage write occurs before the call to a function that may terminate early using inline assembly return(...) or stop().
- (4) Conditional Early Termination: The function called has a code path that conditionally terminates early (using inline assembly) and another path that returns to the caller.
- (5) Control Flow Path After the Write: The continuing control flow path either: Overwrites the initial storage write, reverts.
- (6) Complex Control Flow: The storage write and the early termination can occur within complex control flow structures or arbitrarily nested function calls.

Keccak256 Reuse Error.

- (1) Multiple Keccak-256 Computations: Computing multiple Keccak-256 hashes of the same content but with different lengths inside inline assembly.
- (2) Optimizer Enabled: The optimizer must be enabled for the bug to manifest.
- (3) Memory Content: Keccak-256 hashes of the same memory content but different sizes are considered equal.
- (4) Specific Lengths: The lengths of the Keccak-256 computations, when rounded up to the nearest multiple of 32, are the same.
- (5) Content Deduction: The memory contents at different positions can be deduced to be equal.

Immutable Mutation.

- (1) Immutable Variables of Signed Integer Type: The bug is triggered when using immutable variables of a signed integer type that is shorter than 256 bits.
- (2) Use of Inline Assembly: The unclean value can only be accessed using inline assembly. Without inline assembly, the Solidity compiler performs additional cleanup, preventing the bug from manifesting.
- (3) Legacy Code Generator: The bug is present in the legacy code generator of the Solidity compiler. The new Yul-IR-based code generator correctly implements cleanup for immutable values.

ABI Encoding Error.

- (1) Last Component of the Tuple: The last component of the tuple must be a statically-sized calldata array with the base type being either uint or bytes32 (e.g., bytes32[10] or uint[2][2][2]).
- (2) Dynamic Component in the Tuple: The tuple must contain at least one dynamic component, such as bytes or a struct containing a dynamic array.